

Reconciling Islam and Progress: Elmalılı Hamdi Yazır's Perspective on Culture, Religion, and Modernization

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Abstract: This article examines Elmalılı Hamdi Yazır's contribution to intellectual debates in the late Ottoman period, marked by tensions between tradition and progress, through the *Dibâçe* (foreword) he wrote for the Turkish translation of *Histoire de la Philosophie, Les Problèmes et Les Écoles*. In this 40-page foreword, Yazır, an Ottoman scholar educated in both traditional and modern institutions, discusses the relationship between Islam and Western philosophy/science in the context of the debate over whether Islam is an obstacle to progress. He argues that, in contrast to the conflict between Christianity and philosophy/science in the West, Islam is inherently compatible with both. Rejecting the distinction between the material and spiritual realms, he asserts that God established the unity of them. Therefore, he argues that existence cannot be comprehended solely through scientific reasoning and that a connection between the spiritual and material perspectives is essential. Yazır takes a clear stance against the positivist and materialist understanding of existence and criticizes these approaches for focusing solely on reason and ignoring conscience, emotion and metaphysics. According to Yazır, progress is goal-oriented and that there can be as many goals as there are people on Earth. He therefore criticizes the universal understanding of progress established by Western civilization. In response to the suggestion that the survival and progress of the Ottoman Empire could only be achieved by abandoning Islam and embracing Western values entirely, he argues that progress is not about rejecting past values, but rather perfecting them through new discoveries. He asserts that every science has both a transmitted (nakliyet) and a rational (akliyet) aspect that cannot be considered independently of one another. Therefore, he argues that the Islamic community should embrace the knowledge of the past and benefit from today's scientific developments, advocating the selective adoption of Western knowledge. Evoking a form of cultural essentialism, Yazır calls for the preservation of the religion that forms the essence of Ottoman culture and identity. In this regard, he rejects the wholesale adoption of Western values. His openness to Western thought and science reflects his pragmatic approach to finding solutions to the challenges of his time. The article emphasizes that Yazır acted within a multicultural framework, aiming to keep Islamic culture competent to modern conditions by embracing the appropriation of modern philosophical and scientific ideas, while resisting the political and cultural hegemony of the West. His efforts to reconcile these elements are important as they reflect the complex interplay between tradition and modernity in the late Ottoman intellectual milieu.

Keywords: Elmalılı Hamdi Yazır, Late Ottoman Intellectual Thought, Cultural Identity, Modernization, Islam and Progress, Essentialism.

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İslam ile Terakkiyi Uzlaştırmak: Elmalılı Hamdi Yazır'ın Kültür, Din ve Modernleşmeye Bakış Açısı

Öz: Bu makale, Elmalılı Hamdi Yazır'ın, gelenek ve ilerleme arasındaki gerilimin damgasını vurduğu geç Osmanlı dönemi entelektüel tartışmalarına, *Histoire de la Philosophie, Les Problèmes et Les Écoles*'in Türkçe çevirisi için yazdığı *Dibâçe* (önsöz) aracılığıyla yaptığı katkıyı incelemektedir. Geleneksel ve modern kurumlarda eğitim görmüş bir Osmanlı alimi olan Yazır, 40 sayfalık bu önsözde, İslam'ın ilerlemenin önünde bir engel olup olmadığı tartışması bağlamında İslam ve Batı felsefesi/bilimi arasındaki ilişkiyi ele almaktadır. Yazır, Batı'da Hristiyanlık ile felsefe/bilim arasındaki çatışmanın aksine, İslam'ın her ikisiyle de doğası gereği uyumlu olduğunu savunur. Maddi ve manevi alemler arasındaki ayrımı reddeden Yazır, ikisinin birliğini Tanrı'nın kurduğunu iddia eder. Bu nedenle, varlığın yalnızca bilimsel akıl yürütmeye anlaşılamayacağını ve maddi ve manevi bakış açıları arasında bir bağlantının gerekli olduğunu savunur. Yazır, varlığa ilişkin pozitivist ve materyalist anlayışa karşı açık bir tavır alır ve bu yaklaşımları yalnızca akla odaklanıp vicdan, duygu ve metafiziği görmezden geldiği için eleştirir. Yazır'a göre ilerleme hedef odaklıdır ve yeryüzünde insan sayısı kadar hedef olabilir. Bu nedenle, Batı medeniyetinin oluşturduğu evrensel ilerleme anlayışını eleştirir. Osmanlı İmparatorluğu'nun varlığının ve ilerlemesinin ancak İslam'ı terk edip Batı değerlerini tamamen benimsemekle mümkün olabileceği yönündeki görüşe karşılık, ilerlemenin geçmiş değerleri reddetmek değil, yeni keşiflerle onları mükemmelleştirmek olduğunu savunur. Her bilimin birbirinden bağımsız olarak değerlendirilemeyecek nakliyet (aktarılan) ve akliyet (akılsal) yönleri olduğunu iddia eder. Bu doğrultuda, İslam toplumunun geçmişin bilgisini benimsemesi ve günümüzün bilimsel gelişmelerinden yararlanması gerektiğini savunarak, Batı bilgisinin seçici bir şekilde alınmasını savunur. Bir tür kültürel özcülüğü çağrıştıran Yazır, Osmanlı kültürünün ve kimliğinin özünü oluşturan dinin korunmasını ister. Bu bağlamda, Batı değerlerinin toptan benimsenmesini reddeder. Batı düşüncesine ve bilimine açık tutumu, zamanının sorunlarına çözüm bulma konusundaki pragmatik yaklaşımını yansıtmaktadır. Makale, Yazır'ın çokkültürlü bir çerçeve içinde hareket ettiğini, Batı'nın siyasi ve kültürel hegemonyasına direnirken, modern felsefi ve bilimsel fikirlerin benimsenmesini savunarak İslam kültürünü modern koşullara uygun hale getirmeyi amaçladığını vurgulamaktadır. Yazır'ın bu unsurları uzlaştırma çabaları, geç Osmanlı dönemi entelektüel ortamında gelenek ve modernite arasındaki karmaşık etkileşimi yansıttığı için önemlidir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Elmalılı Hamdi Yazır, Geç Osmanlı Dönemi Entelektüel Düşüncesi, Kültürel Kimlik, Modernleşme, İslam ve İlerleme, Özcülük.

Introduction

Intellectual debates in the late Ottoman period revolved around key concepts of the modernization efforts, such as reorganization (Tanzimat), reform (Islahat), and progress (Terakki). During this period, the Ottoman Empire confronted considerable challenges from Western powers, leading to profound concerns regarding the survival of the state. The central question was how the Ottoman state and society could survive without losing their Ottoman identity. Both officials and intellectuals sought to identify strategies to address these challenges. The reform program known as *Tanzimat* emerged in 1839 as a result of these efforts. This is a significant state reorganization program that exhibited substantial Western influence, particularly with regard to education, institutions, law, and the rights of minorities (Gündüz, 2009; Özervarlı, 2007).

This program resulted in changes, including the emergence of new schools providing Western-oriented education, leading to generations that were increasingly exposed to Western ideas, including radical movements such as positivism and materialism. As Özervarlı points out, the demand for modernization intensified due to increased travel to Western European countries. Consequently, interest in Western science and thought grew, as did the translation of major intellectual texts. Modern, Western-educated Ottomans began arguing that the survival of the state and society depended on adopting Western science, which marked a shift in intellectual discourse

(Özervarli, 2007). Ottoman culture and Islam, regarded as the primary impediments to progress, came under scrutiny. Beşir Fuad, Abdullah Cevdet, and Baha Tevfik, for example, adopted a materialist perspective, asserting the preeminence of science in all facets of life (Hanioğlu, 2013). Intellectual life in the imperial capital was influenced by Auguste Comte's positivism, Ludwig Büchner's materialism, and French spiritualism (Gunasti, 2019). According to Doğan, the debate over whether Islam is an obstacle to progress was particularly heated among West-oriented intellectuals, nationalists, and Islamists during the Second Constitutional Era of the Ottoman Empire. Although Islamists criticized these claims, Doğan noted that they were influenced by them and tried to prove the opposite¹ (Doğan, 2010).

Along with the new schools, the traditional madrasas continued to exist; yet, their members were mostly excluded from the aforementioned debates. However, as Özervarli points out, a new generation of religious scholars emerged in this period. These scholars sought an alternative form of modernization and were influenced by different sources of European thought. They were also educated both traditionally and modernly. This alternative form allows for the preservation of the essence of their culture while allowing for progress (Özervarli, 2007). Elmalılı Hamdi Yazır stands out as one of the leading figures of this group (Işık, 2021). One of the Western sources that influenced Yazır was French spiritualism. Gunasti points out that spiritualism, as embodied in the works of Paul Janet, whom Yazır translated from French, attracted attention because it rejected Cartesian dualism and did not reduce perception to the observable. Thus, it left room for belief in God (Gunasti, 2019). Using philosophical arguments, Yazır tried to show that Islam was not an obstacle to progress. In this article, I will closely examine Yazır's ideas, particularly his famous *Dibâçe* (foreword) to *Histoire de la Philosophie, Les Problèmes et Les Écoles* as the translator (Yazır, 2011). Mehmed Emin Erişirgil, a philosophy lecturer at the Ottoman university Darülfünun, wrote a review of the translated book, emphasizing the importance of the foreword in the following words:

"The *Dibâçe* is more valuable than the book. If this *Dibâçe* had been published separately, it would not have lost its value. For when you read it from beginning to end, you immediately realize that you are under the influence of an intellect that grasps philosophical questions. (...) This *Dibâçe* is the work of a pen that possesses philosophical power" (Köksal, 2011, 19).

This 40-page foreword is a valuable source of information about Yazır's positioning of Ottoman and Islamic culture against the West. The text is indicative of the intellectual debates of the time, as well as Yazır's arguments against Western challenges. In this article, we posit that culture is a field of struggle and that Yazır participated in this type of struggle.

Intellectual and Political Trajectory of Elmalılı Hamdi Yazır

Ismail Kara argues that treating scholars, intellectuals, and their ideas as if they exist outside of time and place prevents us from truly understanding them and the depth of their ideas. He believes these individuals are products of the expectations, feelings, and quests of the periods in which they

¹ As Gündüz demonstrates, the perspectives of these modern, Western-educated individuals profoundly influenced the founding members of the Turkish Republic, which was established following the dissolution of the Ottoman Empire (Gündüz, 2009).

were born. They are also the interpreters of those periods. Kara states that the greatest problem with studies on Yazır and other scholars is that they fail to contextualize them (Kara, 2015). To avoid making a similar mistake, it is useful to briefly examine Yazır's background. Doing so will help place him and his ideas in the foreword in their proper context.

Elmalılı Hamdi Yazır was born in 1878 in Elmalı, a district in Antalya. After receiving his early education in Elmalı, he moved to Istanbul to continue his studies. During this time, he obtained a law degree. From 1905 to 1908, he lectured at the Bayezid Mosque while educating himself in literature, philosophy, and language. He learned French through his own efforts. He entered politics due to the circumstances of his time, and supported constitutionalism, but not the Western version. Rather, he favored a constitutional monarchy in accordance with Sharia law. Because of his support for constitutionalism, he joined the Union and Progress Party (İttihat ve Terakki), and became a member of the First Assembly of the Second Constitutional Period. He played an important role in dethroning Abdülhamid II by convincing Nuri Efendi, the fetva emini (assistant to the Şeyhülislâm), to sign a fatwa he had prepared. He also became Minister of Imperial *Evkâf* during Damat İbrahim Pasha's government. Following the establishment of the republic, he was arrested and sentenced to death for serving in Damat İbrahim Pasha's government during the Turkish War of Independence. However, he was found innocent and released. He then focused on translating a French book on the history of philosophy into Turkish. The *Dibâce* examined in this article is actually the foreword to that book. Later, the Presidency of Religious Affairs commissioned him to translate the Qur'an into Turkish (Yavuz, 1995; Efendioğlu, 2015; Köksal, 2011; Gunasti, 2019). For that reason, he is more widely recognized in Türkiye as the translator of the Qur'an (Gunasti, 2019; Köksal, 2011).

Kurzman and Owens identified three approaches to studying intellectuals. These approaches classify intellectuals as "class-in-itself," "class-bound," or "classless" groups. The class-in-itself approach pioneered by Julien Benda, for example, argues that intellectuals form a separate social class with their own interests. However, Antonio Gramsci's class-bound approach does not view intellectuals as an autonomous group. Rather, it relates them to existing social classes, viewing them as representatives of these classes. Finally, Karl Mannheim's classless approach grants intellectuals a relatively classless status. According to this approach, intellectuals have the potential to transcend their class origins through education (Kurzman and Owens, 2002). When we examine Yazır's life in light of these approaches, his unique position makes it difficult to categorize him.

Examining Yazır's life reveals that it coincided with the Ottoman Empire's decline in the face of the Great Powers, the emergence of nationalist movements, and significant population displacement within the empire. He witnessed the empire's entry into the First World War, its subsequent dissolution and the foundation of the new republic (Gunasti, 2019). He is therefore a product of the transition from the Ottoman Empire to the Republic of Türkiye. During this difficult period, he experienced radical cultural and social changes. He was both an Islamic commentator, trying to solve the daily challenges to Islam in his time, and a thinker trying to find solutions to the influence of positivism in the empire. Unlike the positivists, he believed that religion and philosophy/science were not in conflict with each other. Through his articles in journals such as *Sırat-i Müstakim*,

Sebilürreşad and *Beyanülhak*, he attempted to demonstrate that there was no contradiction between Ottoman tradition and modernization, or between Islam and science (Gunasti, 2019; Coşkun, 2015; Köksal, 2011). For example, Yazır's article "Müslümanlık Mani'-i Terakki Değil, Zamin-i Terakkidir" (Islam is Not an Obstacle to Progress, but a Guarantee of It), which was published in the prominent journal *Sebilürreşad* during the Second Constitutional Era of the Ottoman Empire, was written at the request of Turkish students studying in the United States (Yazır, 2011). The students organized a conference to discuss whether Islam was an obstacle to progress or not and requested his perspective on the matter. The main points of this article are also presented in the foreword. However, the foreword goes further by examining the main arguments of Western philosophy in relation to the fundamental principles of Christianity and Islam. This makes the foreword a more comprehensive piece.

As a representative of a group seeking an alternative form of modernity that reflects both traditional and modern education, Yazır exhibits characteristics that fit each of the three categories identified by Kurzman and Owens (2002). However, it is difficult to categorize him using only one of these classifications. Consequently, we argue that he occupies a distinctive position among his contemporaries.

Western Thought and Its Impact on the Late Ottoman Intellectuals

In order to understand the influence of Western civilization and ideas on the Ottoman Empire and its intellectuals, it is necessary to first take a general look at the Enlightenment period (late 17th century to early 19th century), which was an intellectual and philosophical movement that took place in Europe.

As George Ritzer explains, the Enlightenment was a period of significant intellectual and philosophical change. Many long-standing ideas that had previously been used to organize social life were discarded. Thinkers of this period drew their ideas from two sources: seventeenth-century science and philosophy. They believed that ideas had to be derived from and tested in the real world. In other words, they based their views on empirical research and reason. They believed that the scientific method could solve the problems of social life. Enlightenment thinkers were essentially characterized by the idea that the universe could be understood and controlled through reason and science. Just as the natural world is governed by physical laws, they believed that social life was also subject to certain discoverable laws. This perspective is characterized by opposition to traditional authorities, such as religion (Ritzer, 2011). For example, Auguste Comte developed a scientific philosophy known as positivism. He introduced the term "positivist" into the French language and coined the term "sociology." According to the principles of positivism, there is only one world and science is the sole source of knowledge. The scientific method is the only means by which knowledge can be gained through observation and reason (Bryant, 1985). In other words, the validity of knowledge depends on its scientific basis. Knowledge does not originate from religious or metaphysical concepts, but rather from empirical observations. This standpoint asserts the primacy of a singular methodology that finds application in both physical and social domains. As İbrahim Coşkun notes, these ideas led to a process of secularization that reached its peak in the nineteenth

century, resulting in the rise of radical positivist and materialist thought. He then argues that rationalism, materialism, positivism, the theory of evolution, and the mechanistic worldview were the positivist and materialist movements that influenced the Islamic world (Coşkun, 2015).

Following the scientific revolution, especially in the 19th century, the superiority of the Western world over the rest of the world became apparent, both militarily and culturally. The West presented its own experience as the only path to progress for all of humanity (Altun, 2022). When late Ottoman scholars were exposed to Western ideas through educational institutions and translated literature, combined with the crisis that the Ottoman Empire was undergoing, some proposed radical ideas to save society and state. Traditional Ottoman culture and religion were at the center of these discussions. Among these scholars were those who suggested adopting a wholly European worldview as a means of addressing the prevailing crisis (Özervarli, 2007). They suggested that the entire Western civilization, including its values, should be adopted for the sake of progress. Besides, religion should be left to the individuals. Baha Tevfik and Abdullah Cevdet, for example, were among the prominent figures in this sense. For example, Baha Tevfik is widely recognized as a pioneer in spreading materialist views. Abdullah Cevdet, who also contributed to this cause through his translations, believed that Europe was the only civilization and symbol of progress in the modern world (Coşkun, 2015).

The issue becomes even more complex when religion is involved, particularly Islam, as it shapes one's identity and sense of purpose in this world, as well as determining one's status in the afterlife. It is well known that religion and culture are closely linked. It is fair to say that Ottoman culture was largely based on and nourished by Islam. Therefore, the debate on whether Islam was an obstacle to progress was an important topic of discussion that concerned almost everyone in the Ottoman Empire. This debate was sparked by Ernest Renan's famous lecture on Islam and science at the University of Sorbonne in Paris, to which many people from the Islamic world wrote refutations (Guida, 2011; İhsanoğlu, 2020). Renan began his lecture by stating that, in his time, people with even little education would see the inferiority of Islamic countries, the corruption of states ruled by Islam and the intellectual sterility of peoples who adopted this culture. In short, he argued that Islam and science were incompatible; that the Islamic world's past achievements in science and philosophy were made in spite of Islam; and that most of these achievements were made by non-believers, followers of other religions, or non-Arabs. Essentially, he claimed that the Islamic faith was closed to progress (Renan, 2018).

In this sense, Yazır's ideas may be considered as a refutation against the discourse that Islam is an obstacle to progress. Additionally, the foreword offers insights into Yazır's approach to navigating the cultural differences between Eastern and Western societies. In this regard, an examination of the concept of culture and the underlying power dynamics is necessary.

Examining the Concept of Culture

Culture is a difficult concept to define. Throughout history, every society has developed its own unique culture. If society is defined as a form of interaction, then culture can be seen as its content.

Thomas Hylland Eriksen highlights a dilemma in defining culture; from one perspective, culture is what distinguishes humans from animals and represents a universal human condition. However, from another perspective, culture is what distinguishes us from other peoples. As Eriksen puts it, culture refers to both “basic similarities and to systematic differences between humans” (Eriksen, 2015, 4). Raymond Williams’ seminal work on the subject identifies three primary uses of the term “culture.” Firstly, it is associated with civilization. Secondly, it is used to describe an entire way of life. Thirdly, it is associated with artistic works and intellectual practices (Williams, 2008). The second definition, culture as a way of life, lies at the heart of contemporary debates about identity and politics because it sees culture as the property of a particular people. This view assumes that culture is static, fixed, frozen and rooted. This is known as the essentialist view of culture.

According to Luke J. Buhagiar and et al., “an essential category is commonly understood to be natural, immutable, historically stable, capable of informing or shaping the features of its members, discrete, bounded, exclusive and homogeneous” (Buhagiar et al., 2018, 562). In this view, culture has an essence without which it cannot be defined. However, we know that throughout history, culture has emerged from interaction, not isolation. In that sense, culture has always been fluid. For political scientist Parekh, culture “has no essence,” it is a “historically created system of meaning and significance”, it is “constantly contested, subject to change ... its identity ... never settled, static and free of ambiguity” and also “not a passive inheritance but an active process of creating meaning” (Parekh, 2000 as cited in Grillo, 2003, 160). Therefore, citing Latour’s well-written paragraph on the subject, Don Mitchell suggests that we should focus on how the idea of culture developed as a means to control, order, and define “others.”

“What are often called ‘structure of language’, ‘taxonomy’, ‘culture’, ‘paradigm’ or ‘society’ can all be used to define one another: these are some of the words used to summarise the set of elements that appear to be tied to a claim that is in dispute. These terms always have a very vague definition because it is only when there is a dispute, as long as it lasts, and depending on the strength exerted by dissenters that words such as ‘culture’, ‘paradigm’ or ‘society’ may receive a precise meaning ... In other words, no one lives in a ‘culture’, shares a ‘paradigm’, or belongs to a ‘society’ before he or she clashes with others (Original emphases)” (Latour, 1987 as cited in Mitchell, 1995, 108).

Mitchell (1995) emphasizes the power dynamics behind specific notions of culture. He argues that culture’s power stems from the difficulty of defining it. The question of who reifies this abstract and fluid phenomenon provides insight into power relations. In conclusion, culture can be viewed as an arena where definitions of right and wrong are negotiated, social hierarchies are established, and “the other” is defined. As people are born and raised in specific cultures, culture becomes their most significant investment and the “core of their identity” (Grillo, 2003, 160). Culture is so pervasive and ingrained in a given society that its influence often escapes the awareness of its members. Thus, culture acts as an invisible set of rules that shapes our lives and decisions. Culture’s power lies in its ability to normalize and define what is right or wrong. In this way, culture shapes personal and collective interests. Therefore, Western dominance posed not only a military challenge but also a cultural one to the rest of the world. Exposure to Western ideologies and worldviews created a sense

of cultural loss. This led to the rise of an essentialist view of culture within these societies. We argue that Yazır, a prominent figure of the late Ottoman Empire, adopted a similar stance.

Yazır's Approach to Culture, Religion, and Progress

The foreword he wrote for his translation of *Histoire de la Philosophie, Les Problèmes et Les Écoles* is a key source for understanding Yazır's notion of culture, and his views on the relationship between Islam, philosophy, and progress. In the foreword, he responds to Western criticisms of Islam and to those who argue that adopting Western values is necessary for progress. He also responds to classical scholars who hesitate to embrace developments in the West because they fear becoming like Westerners.

Yazır begins by praising Allah, whom he believes establishes the connection between conscience (vicdan) and existence (vucüd). He defines conscience as the ability to perceive oneself and God, and existence as a state of being. He argues that existence only gains meaning through the conscience. Therefore, he rejects the distinction between the visible and inner worlds, asserting that God established the unity of them. Without this unity, he claims, the soul could not affect the body, nor could the body affect the soul. The individual's self arises from this unity. Thus, from the outset, Elmalılı critiques positivist and materialist worldviews. He asserts that the existence cannot be comprehended solely through scientific reasoning, and that a connection between the spiritual and material realms is essential. Consequently, Yazır's work demonstrates a clear stance against positivist and materialist understanding of existence.

Yazır emphasized that the Islamic ummah should take the lead in science, justice and civilization compared to other nations, referencing hadiths and verses from the Qur'an. However, he noted that today's Islamic ummah, having lost the scientific heritage of the past, is also lacking in the sciences of the present. This has weakened the Islamic world in the face of the West, exposing it to cultural invasion (tehlike-i istimplâle). To avoid this fate, he argued that past knowledge should be combined with modern science to achieve intellectual independence, enabling the ummah to submit only to Allah. Yazır sought to change societal prejudice against Western philosophy and other disciplines, arguing that the West had translated and benefited from the most important books of the Islamic world, including the Qur'an. He also noted that some had even attempted to derive conclusions that would distort the fundamental principles of Islam. He asked, "Why should we deprive ourselves of the scientific treasures of the West?" In this sense, he proposed adopting Western knowledge and reconstructing it from an Islamic perspective, thereby even making Europe a servant to Islam.

Regarding progress, he asserts that it is a relative concept. For example, in his article "Müslümanlık Mani'-i Terakki Değil, Zamin-i Terakkidir," Yazır (2011) argues that progress is goal-oriented and that there can be as many goals as there are people on Earth. He therefore criticizes the universal understanding of progress established by Western civilization. In the foreword, Yazır also addresses the issue of progress. In response to those who suggested that the survival and progress of the Ottoman Empire could only be achieved by abandoning Islam and fully embracing the West, he

argued that progress is not about rejecting past values but rather perfecting them through new discoveries (knowledge). He believes that every science has both a transmitted (nakliyet) and a rational (akliyet) aspect, which cannot be considered independently of one another. On this subject, he argued:

“In ancient times, scientific jurisprudence did not accept excessive division. Philosophy encompassed all sciences. A philosopher was also a jurist (müctehid) in various scientific fields. A philosopher was both a mathematician, a natural scientist, and even a physician. In later periods, the division of scholarship became a necessity. As a result, today absolute jurists are not individuals but communities” (Yazır, 2011, 382).

Therefore, he emphasized the importance of values and social bonds among jurists from different fields within society. According to Yazır, the joint work of these jurists is only possible under the rule of a social principle, which he calls the spirit of society (ruh-i ictimai). Philosophy is necessary for different sciences to gain social value, and therefore it is important that philosophy be compatible with religion. Just as science discovers the laws of nature, philosophy enables the discovery of the true religion. Philosophers entered into conflict with religion because they could not see this truth. Yazır stated that even positivists who oppose religion ultimately feel the need for it and attempt to create a new religion. He argues that the injustices, wars, and hatred in today’s world are the result of spiritual decay in the West. Yazır further argues that the conflict between Western philosophy and religion stems from the Christian belief in the Trinity because it defies reason. In contrast to the conflict between religion and science in the West, Yazır concludes that Islam and science are harmonious. The West fears that one day, Muslims will achieve this harmony, exalt the sanctity of human rights, and set an example for the rest of humanity. To prevent this, Yazır argues that the West has attempted to impose its values and social structure, initiating an artificial debate about whether Islam is an obstacle to progress. Yazır also argues that, while Western philosophy has made progress on the issue of the oneness of God, it has neglected the issue of prophethood. This is important because prophets, rather than philosophers, introduce religion. He posed this challenge to the Islamic world as well: Prophethood must be grounded in reason and experience, and the Islamic world must not fall into the same trap as the West. To make progress, Yazır recommends harmony between reason and religion, developing a sense of law and justice, and preserving religious sensitivity.

Yazır’s inclusion of Western scholars, such as Alexandre Baine and John Stuart Mill, in his lectures indicates his openness to diverse intellectual influences and his willingness to engage with ideas from the Western world. For example, in his foreword, Yazır explains why he chose to translate the book from French, believing its unique content could help Islamic scholars learn Western philosophy. Yazır asserts that Islamic societies should embrace knowledge from the past and present as followers of the Prophet Muhammad. Believing that Muslims should be independent of other societies in order to serve God alone, Yazır criticizes Islamic societies for lacking knowledge of both the old and new sciences. According to him, this situation runs the risk of becoming like the West. He is concerned that society might lose its societal conscience (ictimai vicdan), since it would be equal to losing its soul, its essence. Considering religion an integral part of this conscience, he naturally opposes the materialistic and positivistic views of Western intellectuals. He criticizes Büchner, Kant, and Comte, showing the contradictions and shortcomings of their ideas. Despite progress in science

and technology, he argues that today's atrocities stem from changes in morality arising from materialistic and positivistic ideas that focus solely on reason, ignoring conscience, emotion, and metaphysics. Therefore, Yazır recommends using philosophy to prevent this as it unites reason and conscience, connecting and synthesizing relevant knowledge.

Yazır explains why science did not develop in Muslim society, despite the fact that there is no clash between science, philosophy, and Islam. For him, the backwardness of the Islamic world is due to its lack of readiness towards religion, and the fixation or freezing of its principles (akide). Citing a saying of the Prophet Muhammad, Yazır concludes that Islam is not against progress because, as the Prophet said, every century some people will come and reform the religion. Therefore, he does not have a static view of religion; he believes that changes should be made according to the needs of the times. It is also clear from Yazır's argument that he is open to learning about Western culture and science, as he thinks truth is dynamic. However, his quest for knowledge is fueled by a desire to preserve Islam and its cultural heritage. Although his understanding of religion is open to reform, he believes the essence of religion cannot be touched. Since religion formed the basis of Ottoman culture, Yazır's understanding of culture can be regarded as an essentialist understanding centered on Islam and belief in God. As a devout Muslim, Yazır believed that Islam is the one true religion and that materialism and Christianity are deviations from the truth. His understanding of culture reflects a "them versus us" mentality based on the assumption of an existential conflict between the West and the East. This mentality leads to the fear that becoming like the West will eliminate Ottoman identity. One could argue that Western military and cultural hegemony, as well as Orientalists like Renan, effectively shaped this mentality by causing cultural anxiety within Ottoman society. Considering Renan's argument about Islam and science, as well as the refutations of Islamic thinkers against it, we see that culture acts as a site of contention, a field of war over narratives.

Conclusion

A review of the intellectual debates that arose during the late Ottoman period reveals that they were primarily concerned with forms of modernization, i.e. how to respond to Western military and cultural dominance. Two opposing views emerged from these debates. The first was mainly held by graduates of modern, Western-oriented educational institutions. This view advocated the wholesale adoption of Western values for the salvation of society and the state. The second view, proposed by individuals educated in both traditional and modern institutions, argued for a more selective approach to modernization, whereby Islamic culture would be preserved. Elmalılı Hamdi Yazır, a leading figure in the latter group, sought to reconcile Islam, progress, and modernization through critical analysis.

Believing that the Islamic world should benefit from the scientific treasures of the West, he translated the book *Histoire de la Philosophie, Les Problèmes et Les Écoles* from French and wrote a foreword to encourage Islamic scholars to study Western philosophy. In this 40-page foreword, he examined the relationship between religion, science, and philosophy in the context of the key debate of his time, namely whether Islam was an obstacle to progress. Yazır's openness to Western thought, coupled with his defence of Islamic values, represents a remarkable intellectual stance that sheds

light on the late Ottoman period, a time of political and cultural transition. He believed that truth was not fixed and that past knowledge must be perfected through new discoveries. Therefore, he argued that progress could only be achieved in this way. In this sense, he opposes those who advocate abandoning tradition, Islam, for the sake of progress. Evoking a form of cultural essentialism, Yazır demands the preservation of religion because he believes it is the essence of Ottoman culture and identity. In this regard, he rejects the wholesale adoption of Western values. His openness to Western thought and science reflects his pragmatic approach to finding solutions to the challenges of his time. Yazır's concept of progress is noteworthy in that it challenges the Eurocentric concept of progress.

In response to the argument that Islam is an obstacle to progress, Yazır said that Western thought perceives religion as an obstacle to progress because Christianity is incompatible with reason. However, he argues that this is not the case with Islam, citing the Qu'ran and the words of the Prophet as evidence. He also argued that the neglect of conscience in favor of reason in Western thought has caused many atrocities, posing a serious challenge to dominant Western-centric discourses. He is open to Western philosophy and knowledge, yet he also sees the West as an existential other that does not want the Islamic world to develop. For this reason, becoming like the West is perceived as an existential threat and a matter of survival. His understanding signals a "them versus us" mentality. The pervasive military and cultural dominance of the West has also influenced this mentality. Yazır's stance also indicates a fear of losing one's identity in the face of rapid modernization. In this context, his ideas in the foreword offer insights into the conflicts between tradition and modernity, localization and globalization, and how culture can become a site of contention and power relations.

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